

DDE/RW positions in new hAT TEs

CLUSTAL format alignment by MAFFT (v7.505)

DDE/RW residues are marked by '*'

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Sphaeramia_orbi M-----
Labrus_bergylda -----
Labeo_rohita -----
Xiphophorus -----
Xiphophorus_hel -----
Gouania_willden -----
Lates_calcarife M-----
Anolis_caroline M-----
Kryptolebias_ma -----
Anguilla_anguil ML-QVK-----LRI
Larimichthys_cr -----
Chelmon_rostrat -----
Maylandia_zebra -----
Salvelinus_nama -----
Salmo_trutta -----
Oncorhynchus_ki -----
Bufo_bufo -----
malaclemys_terr -----
Trachemys_scrip -----
Etheostoma_spec -----
Scleropages_for ML-QV-----I
Syngnathus_acus -----
Thalassophryne_ -----
Scophthalmus_ma -----
Xenopus_tropica -----
Collichthys_luc -----
Paralichthys_ol M-----
Cottoperca_gobi -----
Alligator_missi MN-RAEEETP-MEGPANLEPPWTPGSLGEMDSLKPEKEQWPKNQGRPRKQMKNVAVNQK
Parambassis_ran -----
Perca_flavescen -----
Gadus_morhua M-----
Archocentrus -----
Takifugu MSHQCQQPSPSLAGGTTAGTP-----
Oryzias_latipes -----
Erpetoichthys -----MAS-----
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Sphaeramia_orbi -----AEGKR---AKTYHFHPEWEQDYFFV-YSHSKPVCLI-CNTTVALAKKGNLEWHF
Labrus_bergylda -----MSFSKCVCLI-CQSTIAIPKKG NVERHF
Labeo_rohita -----MSFSKCICLI-CQSVIAIPKKG NVERHF
Xiphophorus -----
Xiphophorus_hel -----
Gouania_willden -----
Lates_calcarife -----QRKGCLSHLSQAVAVFEEYNLRRHY
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Anolis_caroline -----MSRKRKIDSECRIFKEQWTDYFFV-NYKERAVCLI-CQNIVSVFKEYNMRRHY
Kryptolebias_ma -----MSRKRKVDADGRLFQERWEGEYLFV-LQGERPVCLL-CYEAVSVVKEYNLRRHF
Anguilla_anguil SAIDPEMSRKRKIDAGRQFQERWEGEYMFV-LQGEKPVCLL-CYEAVSVVKEYNLRRHF
Larimichthys_cr -----
Chelmon_rostrat -----MA-KRK--IDNRTFQDRWEANYLFT-TIKDKPVCLV-CGAGVAVIKEYNIRRHY
Maylandia_zebra -----MA-KRK--NENRSFLDRWETEYLFV-YVKDRPVCLV-CGAHVALTKEYNIRRHY
Salvelinus_nama -----MA-KRK--AENRSFLDKWEAEYLFV-YVKDKPVCLV-CGVNVAVSKEYNIRRHY
Salmo_trutta -----
Oncorhynchus_ki -----MKLHF
Bufo_bufo -----MA-KRK--ADNRNFLDRWETEYLFV-YVKDRPVCLI-CGVNVAITKEYNIRRHY
malaclemys_terr -----
Trachemys_scrip -----MA-KRKIDSENRFQSRWENEYMFV-EIAGKPVCLL-CGSNIAVMKEYNLRRHY
Etheostoma_spec -----MA-KRKMYSERIFQSRWENEYMFV-EIAGKLVCLL-CGSNVAVMKEYNLRRHY
Scleropages_for AKLALTMP-KRKVDSENRAFKNRWEAEYMFV-DIAGKPVCLI-CGANVAVIKEFDLRRHY
Syngnathus_acus -----MP-KRKVDSENRAFKNRWEVEYMFV-DIAGKPVCLI-CGANVAVLKEFNLRHY
Thalassophryne_ -----MP-KRKVDSENRAFKNRWEAEYMFV-DIAGKPVCLI-CGDNVAVIKEFNLRHC
Scophthalmus_ma -----MA-KRKVDSENRAFQNRWEAEYMFV-DIAGKPVCLV-CGANVAVIKEFNIRRHY
Xenopus_tropica -----MP-KRKVDSKNRAFKNRWEAEYMFV-DIAGKPLCLI-CGANVAVIKEFNLRHY
Collichthys_luc -----MQYFFV-EHRGTPTCLI-CTEKVAVHKEYNLKRHY
Paralichthys_ol -----ATVKKRKVDGECRVFQEKWTNDFV-EVKGKPVCLV-CGEALAVMKKANVERHY
Cottoperca_gobi -----
Alligator_missi NDLMSTSKKRKVDTERVFNKKWTSKYFFT-EMGKAFCLI-CKESLAVFKEYNLNRHF
Parambassis_ran -----
Perca_flavescen ---MSAHARKRKVDAECRIFNKNWTAKYLFT-EVGGKAVCLV-CGERIAVFKDYNLSRHY
Gadus_morhua -----ERQWHTDKRKFKKCEWHDYLFV-EVDSNAICLV-CKQKVAVLKEYNIRRHY
Archocentrus -----MAKRRKDEEYRTFQEWTFEFAFV-ERAGSAVCLI-CSDKIASMKRSNIKRHF
Takifugu TTVSMKRAQKRKNSEENREFNAAWTSFAFTAANDAGLPACLI-CGEKLSNNKSNVERHF
Oryzias_latipes -----MMDKRKISEDNRFTNATWADSAFTADETGLPVCLI-CGEILANDKKSNNVARHF
Erpetoichthys -----TKKKRTEEEHREFNRDWTLEFAFICNSDGLPTCLI-CHEKLAHNKSNLERHF

Sphaeramia_orbi KTVH--RSYERDFPAKTLRATKVRDLKAQLAARQSIFTPKTQSKAATIASYRVSHVLA
Labrus_bergylda RTAH--KNYNTNFPKSELKRKVKELKCLSGQQSFFSQPTLKAKAATEASFRVSHLIV
Labeo_rohita RTVH--KNYDTPFPKSELKRKRVKELKSQLSGQQSFFSQLTSKGKAATEASFRVSHLIV
Xiphophorus -----
Xiphophorus_hel -----
Gouania_willden -----MRADKLAKLKSGLLTQNTFVVRQAQLNQASIRAGFWAQLIA
Lates_calcarife ESRH--KDKYDSL--QGQMRADKLSKLSGLLAQNTFVVRQAQLNQSSVRASFRVAQLIA
Anolis_caroline QTQH--KDKYDCL--VGEVRKDKILKLNILTTQNTFVKQKQLNIISSLRASFVAKLIA
Kryptolebias_ma DTKH--GAKYAQA--SLQEQQIAQELKGLRSQQSLFTKSTAKNEAAVKASFIVAKEIA
Anguilla_anguil DTKH--GAKYAKV--SLHEKQIVKELKGLRSQQNLFTKATKNDAAVKASFVAAEIEA
Larimichthys_cr -----
Chelmon_rostrat ETKH--YEKYDL--DLKQKLLKVEEMKRSLSRQTLFTKAKSKSEAAVKASFIVAAEIA
Maylandia_zebra ETKH--QEKYDL--DMTQRRRKAEMKRSFVSQQTMFKKAISQSEAAVKASFVAAEIEA
Salvelinus_nama ETKH--HDKYDL--DMTQRSQKIEEMKRSLSVQQNMFKATSQSEAAVKASYIVAAEIEA
Salmo_trutta -MKH--HDKYDL--DMTQRSQKVEEMKRSLSVQQNMFKATSQSEAAVKASYIVAAEIEA
Oncorhynchus_ki -LGHGQTLARDL--DMTHRSQKVEEMKRSLSVQQNMFKATSQSEAAVKASYIVAAEIEA
Bufo_bufo ETKH--HDKCKDL--DMTQKRSQKVEEMKRSLSVQQNMFKATSQSEAAVKASYIVAVEIEA
malaclemys_terr -----
Trachemys_scrip ETKH--ENKFKNL--SAGQKLQKVEELKKNLTSQQTFFTKAKSQSEAAVKASFIVAAEIEA
Etheostoma_spec ETKH--EDKLKNL--SAGQKLQKVEELKKNLTSQQTFFTKAKSQSEAAVKASFIVAAEIEA
Scleropages_for ETKH--QDNLKDLD--NAEQIQAELKKNLTLQQMFFTRAKSQSEAAVKASFIVAEIEA

Syngnathus_acus ETKH--LDNLKDL--NAEQKIQKVEELKKNLTFQQTFFTRAKSQSEAAVKASFIVAEEIA
Thalassophryne_ ETKH--QDNLKDL--NAEQKIQKAEDLKNLTLQQTFFTRAKSQSEAAVKSSFIAAEEIA
Scophthalmus_ma ETKH--QE-LQNL--NAEEKIQRVKEKKNLRFQQTFFTRAKSQSEAAVKASFIVAQEIA
Xenopus_tropica ETKH--QDNLKDL--NAEQKIQKVEELKKNLTLQQTIFTRAKSESEAAVKASFIVAEEIA
Collichthys_luc TTRH--AEEYEKY--QGDERANRIANLKTCLLRQQDFFKKATKESNAAVKASYMVSEMAIA
Paralichthys_ol SSKH--AKLDEL--KGQMXLKDINALRRSLGAQQAAXTRPQTDRENITRASVVSLEIA
Cottoperca_gobi -----
Alligator_missi ETKH--ASKYDKL--SAQEKTKKAEEMVAAMQKEQSFSPKALEVRDGMRTSYEMAHIIA
Parambassis_ran -----MLLAKLQTQQGFFTKLHTSRDAATKTSFLISHKIA
Perca_flavescen ETTT--AEKYKNL--SDAERARTSEALLAKLQKQQGFFTKLHTSRDAATKTSFVISHKIA
Gadus_morhua ETMH--SHQFAKY--TGEDRKVKAAANLLIKLETQQQTLQLPSTAQENATLASYRISNIIV
Archocentrus DTRH--TTFASKYP--AGDSRKKACQELLCKVQASQQQLRVWTQQ--GDWNSASFAGALAIIV
Takifugu QSKH--LAFAEKYP--TEDERQRAISELQRQAEERKLSFKKWISSPQSTTAASFVAAQEIIV
Oryzias_latipes ENKH--SAFAKKYP--KGEERKKAIVSELMQKADVSRSHFKKWIKTGNSTTCTSFVVAQEIIV
Erpetoichthys TKKH--TQFASKYP--AGEERKKAIVDELQKQKQSSSMLSNWTQSTSNVNLASFVLSLEIA

Sphaeramia_orbi KHNPFPKGDIVKEAFLEAADSLFDHFKNKTEIVDAIKGVQLSRNTATRWCMAVDVEE
Labrus_bergylta KNKKSFDGEMVKEAFVEAADSLFRDFKNAEILSSIKALQLSRSTVTRRSEAIADLTQ
Labeo_rohita KNKKSFDGEMVKEAFVEAADSLFRDFKNAEILSSIKALQLSRSTVTRRSEAMAEDLTQ
Xiphophorus -----MSRHTVETRISDINNALES
Xiphophorus_hel -----MSRHTVETRISDINNALES
Gouania_willden SSGKPFDTGDFVKKCLNAVVEVCPDKKQVDF-----NAVSLSASTITRRIIEEIGGNVYA
Lates_calcarife SSGKPFDTGDFVKKCMNAV--EVCPEKKNVF-----NAVSLSVSTITRRIIEEIGGNVYA
Anolis_caroline CTGRPFVEGDFVKKCLLSVAKEMCPEKADLF-----STVSLSGSTITRRIIEEIGGNVYA
Kryptolebias_ma QASKSFSEGAFLKQCMKLVCEQVCPDQLQTF-----KNVLSRNTIANRVKELAEENLTT
Anguilla_anguil RASKSFSEGAFLKQCMKLVCEQVCPDQIQTF-----KNVLSRNTIADRVKELAEENLST
Larimichthys_cr -----
Chelmon_rostrat KSARPFNEGEFVKKCMKVCIVCPDKKQVDF-----SKNVLSRNTMAERVCELSTNLHE
Maylandia_zebra KSARPFSEGEFVKKSCMMK---VCPEKQVDF-----SNVLSRNTVADRTRELANDLNN
Salvelinus_nama KSARPFNEGEFVKKCMKVCIVCPDKKQVDF-----SNVLSRNTVADRTCDLATNLVD
Salmo_trutta KSARPFNEGEFVKKCTMKVCDLVCPEKQVDF-----SNVLSRNTVADRTCDLATNLVD
Oncorhynchus_ki KSARPFNEGEFVKKCMKVCIVCPDKKQVDF-----SNVLSRNTVADRTCDLATNLVD
Bufo_bufo KSARPFNEGEFVKKCMKVCIVCPDKKQVDF-----SNVLSRNTVADRTCDLATNLVD
malaclemys_terr -----MATDLKT
Trachemys_scrip KSGRPFTEGEFVKNCMKVCIVCPDKKQVDF-----ANVLSRNTVANRVCEMATDLKT
Etheostoma_spec KSGRPFTEGEFVKNCMKVCIVCPDKKQVDF-----ANVLSRNTVANRVCEMATDLKT
Scleropages_for KSARPFTEGEFLKSCMIKVFVCLCPDKKQVDF-----ANVLSRNTIADRVCEMATDLRT
Syngnathus_acus KAGRPFTEGEFLKSCMIKVFVCLCPDKKQVDF-----ANVLSRNTVADRVCEMATDLRT
Thalassophryne_ KSARPFTEGEFLKSCMIKVFVCLCPDKKQVDF-----ANVLSRNTIADRVCEMATDLRT
Scophthalmus_ma KSARPFTEGEFLKSCMIKVFVCLCPDKKQVDF-----ANVLSRNTVADRVCEMATDLRT
Xenopus_tropica KSARPFTEGEFLKSCMIKVFVCLCPDKKQVDF-----AN-----
Collichthys_luc TAGKPFTEGEFVKKCILQAASIIICPEKKGQF-----SNISLSANTVAERISDLSNDIYD
Paralichthys_ol TKLKPHAEGEFVKECLVAAEELAPDKVKSF-----QSVLSRRTVSRITDMAQDIEK
Cottoperca_gobi -----MVETSELLCPESKGF-----EKISLSRRTVTRRVELIDEDIVR
Alligator_missi KSKPFSEGEFVKECLVSAALICPDKKEQF-----ENVLSRRTIVRRVEDISENLHQ
Parambassis_ran KNSKPFSEGEFVKECLVSAALICPDKKEQF-----EQVPLSRRTVTRRIEQIAGNLEL
Perca_flavescen KNSKPFSEGEFVKECLVSAALICPEKKGAF-----EQVPLSRRTVTRRIEQIAGNLEL
Gadus_morhua RSGHAFAGDFVKECLVAAEAVCPTQKRAF-----SQISLSRNTVTRRVEDMAEDVRG
Archocentrus RNGKPFDTGEYAKTFMLDVASELFDVSDKDKIMKRIKDMPLSARTVHDRTIMMANQIEE
Takifugu RRGKPFDTGEYIKETFIQISEHLFSDFKNKNEIVQKIKDMPLSAKTVDRTIKMAANISS
Oryzias_latipes KHGKPFDTGEYIKETFIKISKHLFSDFKNKNEILQKIKDMPLSAKIVQDRSVNMAENVTR

Erpetoichthys KKGKPFDTGGEYVKDCFIRASEELFRDFKNKPEILKKIKDLPLSAKTVDRIAKMSSNVTY

Sphaeramia_orbi QLRRDIDACECFSLQFDESTDMVDVAQLCVFIRMVFEDEMSTKEELLTILPLKGHTRGEDI
Labrus_bergylta QLWKDIADCECFSLQLDESTDVSDTAQLCIFIRMVFTDMTAKEELLTLLPMKEHTRGEDI
Labeo_rohita QLWKDITDCECFSLQLDESTDVSDTAQLCIFIRMVFNMTAKEELLTVLPMKEHTRGEDI
Xiphophorus DLHADLNACAYFVALDESCDIQDKPQLAIFVRMISEDVCVKEELLDIVPLKDRTRGTDV
Xiphophorus_hel DLHADLNACAYFVALDESCDIQDKPQLAIFVRMISEDVCVKEELLDIVPLKDRTRGTDV
Gouania_willden QLQKMKFEFFFLAMDESTDVQDTAQLLIFICGVSANFEMCEEALALQSLKGTMTGEDI
Lates_calcarife QLQKMKFEFFFLALDESTDVQDTVQLRIFIRGVSANFEMCKEALALQSLKGTMTGEDI
Anolis_caroline HLQNSAKKLSYFSLALDESNDVRDSAQLLIFIRGTNDYFEVTEELALQSIKGTMTGEDI
Kryptolebias_ma QLAETRSTYAFSLAVDESTDMTDTAQLSIFIRGVKSDLSITEELLDVAALHGTTTGQDI
Anguilla_anguil QLAESRSYAFSLAVDESTDMTMAQLSIFIRGVKSDLSVTEELLDVAAMHGTTTGRDI
Larimichthys_cr --MRKGEDFVAVSLAVDESSDTSQAQLSIFIRGVSNLCVTEELLDGLKSMHGTTTGKDI
Chelmon_rostrat KLIKKGFDFIAYSLAVDESSDTSQAQLSIFIRGVSSLCVTEELLDGLKSVHGTTTGKDI
Maylandia_zebra QLMKGNFVAFSLAMDESSDASDTAQLSVFIRGVSTLCVTEELLDGLKSMHGTTTGKEI
Salvelinus_nama QLMKKGDFVAFSLAVDESCDASDTAQLSVFIRGVSNLCVTEELLDGLKSMHGTTTGKEI
Salmo_trutta QLMKKGDFVAFSLAVDESCDASDTAQLSVFIRGVSNLCVTEELLDGLKSMHGTTTGKEI
Oncorhynchus_ki QLMKKGDFVAFSLAVDESCDASDTAQLSFFIRGVSNLCVTEELLDGLKSMHGTTTGKEI
Bufo_bufo QLLEKGFDFVAFSLAVDESSDASDTAQLSVFIRGVSNMVCVTEELLDGLKSMHGTTTGKEI
malaclemys_terr QLIERAKDFVAVSLAVDETTDATDTAQLAIFIRGVSNLCVTEELLDIKSMHGTTTGKEDI
Trachemys_scrip QLIERAKDFVAVSLAVDETTDATDTAQLAIFIRGVSNLCVTEELLDIKSMHGTTTGKEDI
Etheostoma_spec QLIERAKDFVAVSLAVDETTDSTDTAQLAIFIRGVSNLCVTEELLDIKSMHGTTTGKEDI
Scleropages_for QLSERSKDFIAYSLAVDESTDMTDTAQLAIFIRGVSNLRVTEELLDIKSMHGTTTGKDI
Syngnathus_acus QLSKRSKDFIAYSLAMDESTDMTDTAELAIFIRGVSDLRVTEELLDIKPMHGTTTGKDI
Thalassophryne_ QLSERSKDFIAYSLAVDESTDMTDTAQLAIFIRGVSNLRVTEELLDIKLMHGTTTGKDI
Scophthalmus_ma QLSERSKDFIAYSLAVDESTDMTDTAQLAIFIREVSSLCVTEELLDIKSMHGTTTGKDI
Xenopus_tropica -----
Collichthys_luc QLCEKAKCFSAVSVALDETTDITDTAQLAMYVRGVNDNFVMEELLRVIPMHGQTTAQEI
Paralichthys_ol TLKNTARDFEYFSLACDETTDITHTAQLAIFLRGITSEFETKEELLSLQAMHGTTTGKEDL
Cottoperca_gobi ELNKKVSEFKLYSLALDESNDIKDTAQLLIFIRGINDSFEITEELLSMESLKGKTRGEDL
Alligator_missi QLKSKVNDFSYFALALDDSDCVKGTDQLLIFIRGITENFELTEELALIQSMKDTTTGKDL
Parambassis_ran QLHREVAGDFDFSLALDESCDVRDTAQLLIFVRGITD-FKITEELAAAMRSMKGTGGSDL
Perca_flavescen QLQREVACDFDFSLALDESCDVRDTAQLLPWDYGLQDY-----
Gadus_morhua QIAQRAGRFSAFSIADESTDISDSAQLLVFLRGVNEDFEVCQELAGLETGKGTTRGIDI
Archocentrus TQVKDINAAVFSLALDESTDVSHLSQFSVIARYAVGD-TLHEESLAVLPMKGTTRGEDL
Takifugu KQIDDINSAQAFSIGCESSDVNDIEQIALLCRYANAN-GPQEELIELIPLKGQTRGQDI
Oryzias_latipes QQIEDINSALAYAIACNMSKDKNDIEQIALFCRYVSAA-GPQEEMIELIPLKGQTRGEDI
Erpetoichthys LQVEDIQSSALS LAIDESCDIKDTAQVALFVRYMSSQ-GPKEELGLLPLSGQTRGEDI

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Sphaeramia_orbi FNAFMGFVSGTKLPLFKLISITTDGAPSMVGRSGFIALCK----ESESF-PDILNYHCI
Labrus_bergylta FQSFNNFITKTQLPVYKLVSIITTDGAPAMVGRVNGFIAKCR----EDDAF-PDFLNYHCI
Labeo_rohita FQSFKNFMEKTRLPVCKLVSIITTDGAPAMVGRSNGFIAKCR----EDDAF-PDSLNYHCI
Xiphophorus KEAMMEVFKTANMSLEKLTAIATDGAPSMIGSVNGLVGLCKG----DDLFPDFWNFHCI
Xiphophorus_hel KEAMMEVFKTANMSLEKLTAIATDGAPSMIGSVNGLVGLCKG----DDLFPDFWNFHCI
Gouania_willden FGKVCQTMEEELDLWSKLASITTDGAPSLVGAFRGLIGRMNREIEKRGLT--APLQVHFL
Lates_calcarife FGKVYRTMEEELDLWSKLASITTDGAPSMVGMFRGLIGRMNREMEERGLI--APLQVHCL
Anolis_caroline YEKLCQTVNDLELDWAKLASVTTDGAPSMVGSKKGVIARINQEMDKHNHS--HPIAIHCL
Kryptolebias_ma FDAVEKSVSKNALQWENLVGLTTDGAPAMCGEKAGLVGLMRRKMQKMNCH-TPLITYHCI
Anguilla_anguil YDAVEKSVSKTGLPWEKLVGLTTDGAPAMCGKAGLVGLMKEKMQKSNCH-TPLITYHCI
Larimichthys_cr FEEVSKCVDEMKL PWDKLVGLTTDGAPAMCGQKSGLVGRMREKMRKQ-A-GELTVYHCI

Chelmon_rostrat FEEVSKITEMSLPWDKLVGLTTDGAPAMCGQKSGLVGRIQEKMREED-A-GKLTVYHCI
 Maylandia_zebra FEEVSKCLTEMKLPWEKLVGLTTDGAPAMCGQRSGLVGRVREKMRAENCA-GELTVYHCI
 Salvelinus_nama FEEVSKCVTEIKLPWDKLVGLTTDGAPAMCGKKSGLVGMVREKMREENCA-GELTVYHCI
 Salmo_trutta FEEVSKCVTEIKLPWDKLVGLTTDGAPAMCGKKSGLVGMVREKMREENCA-----
 Oncorhynchus_ki FEEVSKCVTEIKLPWDKLVGLTTDGAPAMCGKKSGLVGMVREKMREENCA-GELTVYHCI
 Bufo_bufo FEEVSKCVTEIKLSWDKLVGLTTDGAPAMCGKTSGLVGRVREKMQEENCA-GELTVYHCI
 malaclemys_terr FGNVFSVTDKMLPWEKLVGLTTDGAPAMCGEKNGLVGRMRSKMREENCA-----
 Trachemys_scrip FGNVFSVTDKMLPWEKLVGLTTDGAPAMCGEKNGLVGRMRSKMREENCA-GELTVYHCI
 Etheostoma_spec FGNVFSVTDKMLPWEKLVGLTTDGAPAMCGEKKWTGGKDALK---DAG-GELC-----
 Scleropages_for FENVCQSITDMKLPWDKLVGLTTDGAPAMCGEKSGLVGRMRVKMQEENCT-GELTAYHCI
 Syngnathus_acus FENVCQSITDMKLPWDKLVGLTTDGAPAMCGEKSGLVGRMRVKMQEENCT-GELTTYHCI
 Thalassophryne_ FENVCQSITDMKLPWDKLVGLTTDGAPAMCGEKRGLVGRMRVKMQ-ENC-----
 Scophthalmus_ma FENVCQSITDMKLPWDKLVGLTTDGAPAMCGEKLGLVGRMRVKMQEENCT-GELTAYHCI
 Xenopus_tropica -----
 Collichthys_luc FCQLCDAIKNAGLPWKRFGITTINGALSMTRRKNGLVKVVKKLEEEGVE--EAIALHCI
 Paralichthys_ol FNQVIVAMNNFELPFEKLSGIATDGAPAMVGXQKGLTALVKKEMSRSLDPSDLVVCHCI
 Cottoperca_gobi YEQVSAVIERMMLPWSKLANVTTDGGSPNLTKGNVGLLKRIQDKVKEENPD-QDVI FLHCI
 Alligator_missi LEAVDQCVSGLGTDWKKLVSVTTYGSPNLAGKDVGLLKIIQDQVKETDPE-QKII LLHCI
 Parambassis_ran FMEVNACIDTLGLKWDRLAGVTTDGCPLNT-----
 Perca_flavescen -----GGAGSNA-----
 Gadus_morhua FKAVEQVMDKNGLKWENLSGITTDGAPAMVGKRALGTALVSDKVRECG---GSIFKYHCI
 Archocentrus FKSFTTEFAGKKNLPMDKLISVCTDGAPCMVGKNRGFVALLREHEK-----RPILSFHCI
 Takifugu CDVVVSLKDKGINTTHLVSVIDGAPSMRGAQKGFVNLQKSLG-----RDLMTFHCI
 Oryzias_latipes CEAVLHCLRTKEIKTTHLVPVADGAPSMGTGAQKGFVALLQKSLD-----RKLLTFHCI
 Erpetoichthys ANAVQKCLEDNKIDLNKIVSIATDGARSMTGKNKGATTILQSKIN-----HEILTFHCI

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Sphaeramia_orbi IHQQVLCGKIL--NMKEVMDVAMKIVCSVRARSLQRRLFRAHLEENDAHEH-TDLLLHTDV
 Labrus_bergylda IHQQALCAKML--NMKEIMDVAMKIACSIRARSLQRRLFRAHLEQADCDH-SELLLHTDV
 Labeo_rohita IHQQALCAKML--NMKEIMDVATKIACSIRARSLQRRLFRAHLENADCDH-SELLLHTDV
 Xiphophorus IHREQLVSKTL--NLDHVMKPMMEIVNYIRTHALTHRQFKNLIADLDGDLPGDPLHCAV
 Xiphophorus_hel IHREQLVSKTL--NLDHVMKPMMEIVNYIRTHALTHRQFKNLIADLDGDLPGDPLHCAV
 Gouania_willden IHQQTLCCCKVL--KWDSVMKVVVSCINFIRANGLKHRQFQQFLTELESAH-GDVLVYTEV
 Lates_calcarife IHQQALCCCKVL--TWDSVMKVVVSCINFIRAKGLKHRQFQEFLESELEPAH-GDVLVYTEV
 Anolis_caroline IHQQALCSKSL--KWDSVMKIVVSCVNFIRANALNHRQFQEFLESELNAA-EDVLVYHTEV
 Kryptolebias_ma IHQEALCGKVL--GMEDIVTTVMKTVNFIRARGLNHRQFQQFLLEMGSEH-GDVPYHTEV
 Anguilla_anguil IHQEALCGKVL--GMDDIMTTVMKTVNFIRARGLNHRQFQLFLQEMGSEY-GDVPYHTEV
 Larimichthys_cr IHQEALCGKAL--KMDHIMSTVTQVNFIRAKGLNHRQFQKSFLEELGADH-SDMPYHTEV
 Chelmon_rostrat IHQEALCGKAL--QMEHVMSSIKGVVNFIRAKGLNHRQFQKSFLEELDSEY-RDVPYHTEV
 Maylandia_zebra IHQESLCGKAL--KMEHVMTAVTRVNFIRAKGLNHRQFQKSFLEECGSEY-GDVPYHTEV
 Salvelinus_nama IHQESLCAKAL--KMEHVMTVTQVNFIRAKGLNHRQFQKSFLEECGSEY-ADVVPYHTEV
 Salmo_trutta -----EECGSEY-ADVVPYHTEV
 Oncorhynchus_ki IHQEALCAKAL--KMEHVMTVTQVNFIRAKGLNHRQFQKSFLEECGSEY-ADVVPYHTEV
 Bufo_bufo IHQESLCGKAL--KMEHVMTVTQVNFIRAKGLNHRQFQKSFLEECGSAY-SDVPNQTEV
 malaclemys_terr -----EPRLNHRQFQSFLEIDSEF-GDMPYHTEV
 Trachemys_scrip IHQESLSAKVL--KMDHVMNTVTQVNFIRAHGLNHRQFQSFLEIDSEF-GDMPYHTEV
 Etheostoma_spec -----RAHGLNHRQFQSFLEIDSEF-GDMPYHTEV
 Scleropages_for IHQEALCGKVL--KMDNVMSLTQTQVNFIRAKGLNHRQFQSFMRIDSEF-ADIPYHTEV
 Syngnathus_acus IHQEALCGKVL--KMDHVMSTVTQVNFIRSRGLNHRQFQSFMRIDSEF-ADIPYHTEV
 Thalassophryne_ -----TEV
 Scophthalmus_ma IHQEMLCCCKVL--KMEHVMTVTQVNFIRAKGLNHRQFQSFMRIDSEF-ADIPYHTEV
 Xenopus_tropica -----

Collichthys_luc IHQQALCSKCL--KFDNVMSVVVKCINQIKSRGLKRRFRFLEEMESEY-GDVLVYFTEV
Paralichthys_ol IHQESLCAHSL--KLNNVMTTVVSTINFIKGRGLNRRQFKELLESEIESEY-GDLVYHCEV
Cottoperca_gobi IHQESLCKSVL--QLNHVDPVVKLVNFIARGLNHRQFITFLEETDADH-QDLLYHSRV
Alligator_missi IHQEVLCCKSVL--KLSTVVDTVTKVVSYIRARGLNHRQFATLLEGESESEH-TDVLHDTSV
Parambassis_ran -----EEHESEH-SDIGYHTAV
Perca_flavescen -----VDERNND-----
Gadus_morhua LHQEQLCAKNI--GLKNVMQDVGIVNNIRSKALSHRQFKAVVDEMDAQY-GDVLVYHCEV
Archocentrus LHQEALCAQMCGEQLGEVMSLVIRVVNFIVARALNDRQFKTLLEEVGNNY-PGLLLHSNV
Takifugu IHQEALCAQTFFPECEVEMNLVIKIVNKIIANGLSHRQFCSLLEEVENY-SDLLLNHRV
Oryzias_latipes LHQEALCAQTFFPECTQVMDLVIQIVNKIMANGLNHRQFRSLLELDSAY-SDLLLNHKV
Erpetoichthys IHQEALCAQTFFPAEIVEVMNLVIKIVNSILSKALHHRQFKELNEMETQY-SDLLLNHKV

Sphaeramia_orbi RWLSRGKFLDRFMELLPEIKDFLRLSKHM--DYHTKLEDHQWLLDLSFLTDLTGELSELN
Labrus_bergylda RWLSRGKFLQRFRELCPEIKEFFRVAGHA--EY-QQLNDGQWLLDLAFLDNLNLDLN
Labeo_rohita RWLSRGKFLQRFRELCPEIKEFLRVAKHA--EY-SQLNDNLWLLDLAFLDNLNLDLN
Xiphophorus RWLSRGKVSRFLELLEPVKLFM-AEKNK--SY-PQLSDPKWMLDLAFLVDMLSHLDKLN
Xiphophorus_hel RWLSRGKVSRFLELLEPVKLFM-AEKNK--SY-PQLSDPKWMLDLAFLVDMLSHLDKLN
Gouania_willden RWLSRGRVLRFFYELLPEINAFI-HLKD--TI-PELIDPEWKWHLAFLTDVTEMLNSLN
Lates_calcarife RWLSRGRVLRFFYELLPEINAFI-HSQNK--TV-PELIEPEWKWHLAFLTDVTEMLNSFN
Anolis_caroline RWLSRGRVLRFFYELLPEINAFI-LSKNK--EV-PELNDAEWWHLAFLTDITELNSFN
Kryptolebias_ma RWLSRSKVLKRFFELREDIAFFM-QSKGK--LM-SELSDPKWLDFAVLCDITDHLAQLN
Anguilla_anguil RWLSRSKILKRFFELREDIALFM-QSKGK--PL-SELSDPNWLDFAVLCDITEHLAQLN
Larimichthys_cr RWLSRGKVAKRFFELREEICLFM-ESKGG--DT-TELREKQFCELAFLCDIMNHLDALN
Chelmon_rostrat RWLSRGKVLNRCFELREEICQFI-ENKGG--DT-TELREKQFCELAFLSDIVSHLDVNL
Maylandia_zebra RWLSRGKVLNRCFELREEIFQFL-ESKGG--DT-AELREQFCELAFLCDITSHLDALN
Salvelinus_nama RWLIRGKVLNRCFELREEICQFL-ETKGG--DT-AELREKQFCELAFLCDISSHLDALN
Salmo_trutta RWLSRGKVLNRCFELHEEICQFL-ETKGG--DT-AELREKQFCELAFLCDISSHLDALN
Oncorhynchus_ki RWLSRGKVLNRCFELSEEICKFL-ETKGG--DT-AELREKQFCELAFLCDISSHLDALN
Bufo_bufo RWLSRGKVLNRCFELHEEICQFL-ESKGG--DT-AELREKVLCELAFLCDISSHLDALN
malaclemys_terr RWLSRGKVLKRHFELREEICQFM-DSKGG--DC-TVLRDEKWKCELFLADITSHLSALN
Trachemys_scrip RWLSRGKVLKRHFELREEICQFM-DSKGG--DC-TVLRDEKWKCELFLADITSHLSALN
Etheostoma_spec RWLSRGKVLKRHFELREEICQFM-DSKGG--DC-TVLRDEKWKCELFLADITSHLSALN
Scleropages_for RWLSRGKVLDRVFELSNEICQFI-DSKGG--DS-TNFRDEKWKCELFLADITAHNLALN
Syngnathus_acus RWLSRGKVLNRVFEELSNEICQFM-DSKGG--DS-TVLRDEKWKCELFLADITAHNLALN
Thalassophryne_ RWLSWGKVLNRVFEELSNEICQFM-DSKGG--DS-TNFRDEKWKCELFLADITAHNLALN
Scophthalmus_ma RWLSRGKVLNRVFEELSKEICQFM-DSKGG--DT-TVLRDEKWKCELFLADITAHNLALN
Xenopus_tropica -----
Collichthys_luc RWLSRGNVLRFFELRAEVKAFM-EKDG--AV-PVLSDPKWLMDLAFLVDITHELVNLN
Paralichthys_ol RWLSRANMLAGFIHC-----GKKSASWR-----
Cottoperca_gobi RWLSLGGKVCQRVWELKEEIRSFL-EQMGKSDEF-PELSDTDWLCDFAFVAVDILSHMNELN
Alligator_missi SWLSLGNILKRVWELRAEIGLFL-NMKED-LDF-PQLNDAEWLSDFAFAIDVTGYMNDLN
Parambassis_ran RWLSLGGKVLKRVWDLNAEIREFC-EKGG--DI-PELSDENWMADFAFAVDVITAHMNELN
Perca_flavescen -----
Gadus_morhua RWLSRGKVLRRFFELREEIRVFQ-ATKEN--NI-QVPSDKHWIADLAFLVDITELNLIN
Archocentrus RWLSRGKVLRSFAACLSEIRTFI-EMKNI--EH-PELANTEWLLKFFYLVDITMTEHLNQLN
Takifugu RWLSGGEVLRKFAACLEHVKTFL-GNKGL--GY-PELEDPSWLEKFFYFVDMTSYLNMNLN
Oryzias_latipes RWLSRGVVLKRFACLEEVKVFV-SNKGL--TF-PELEQPEWQEKLFHMVDMTAAHLNLTN
Erpetoichthys RWLSKGGKVLKRFALCLNEINTFL-NEKGI--NH-PELENDKWLQKFFYFVDMITAKLNELN
**

Sphaeramia_orbi LELQGGKGDVVNMMSSVSTFKSKLKLMSNRLRLGNLCNFPHMQAELQRQGGVT---QL

Labrus_bergylta LELQGGKDKTVINMISSVNAFKRKMQLHSSKLRHDLANVQNLASELEMQKACV----QL
 Labeo_rohita LELQGGKDKTVTNMISSVNAFKRKMQLHSSKLRHDLANFQNLVSELEMQKSCV----QL
 Xiphophorus LDLQGGKDKTLPLDLTQSVFVFNKVKLFKVHIQNGNLSHFPSLRSAAA---QKAGI----RM
 Xiphophorus_hel LDLQGGKDKTLPLDLTQSVFVFNKVKLFKVHIQNGNLSHFPSLRSAAA---QKAGI----RM
 Gouania_willden LQLQGGKGLICDMYSHIKAFEVKLLALLEQVKKHNF IHLPATQNL--STENPAV----PF
 Lates_calcarife LQLQGGKGLICEMYSHIKAFEVKPELLLGQVKKHSF IHLPATQNL--SAENPEV----PF
 Anolis_caroline VQLQGGKGLICDMQSHVKAFAEVKGLLLIKQVKEENFCHLPTTQSL--SAEKPLI----AF
 Kryptolebias_ma QKLQGRKQVITQMSDTITAFQRKLDLWMWQVQDNLVHFPVCQSM--SASFPET----F
 Anguilla_anguil QKLQGRKQVITQMSDMITCFQRKLDLWKWQVEQDNLAHFSVCQSI--SASVPDA----F
 Larimichthys_cr LQLQGRAHVITDMYAVRAFRTKRLWESQMQQGNLAHFLCCQVM--KEQTATA----VM
 Chelmon_rostrat LQLQGRGHVITDMYAAVRAFRTKRLWKTQMLQG---HFPCQTM--AAQISPD----AL
 Maylandia_zebra LQLQGRGRITDMYAVRAFRTKRLWQNLQGNLGHFPCCQMM--NMQISTA----VF
 Salvelinus_nama LQLQGRGRITDMYAAVRAFRTKRLWENQMLQGNPCHFPCCQTI--KAQISTA----VF
 Salmo_trutta LQLQGRGRITDMYAAVRAFRTKRLWENQMLQGNPCHFPCCQTI--KAQISTA----VF
 Oncorhynchus_ki LQLQGRGRITDMYAAVRAFRTKRLWENQMLQGNPCHFPCCQSI--KAQISTA----MF
 Bufo_bufo LQLQGRRRITDMYAAVRAFRTKRLWENQMLQGNLGHFPCCQTM--KTQFFTN----LF
 malaclemys_terr LQLQGREHIITDMHDAVKAFAVQKRLRLWETHMHQCNLSHFPCQVI--RNQESAT----VF
 Trachemys_scrip LQLQGREHIITDMHDAVKAFAVQKRLRLWETQMHQCNLSHFPCQVI--RNQESAT----VF
 Etheostoma_spec LQLQGREHIITDMHDAVKAFAVQKRLRLWETQMHQCNLSHFPCQVI--LNQESDT----VF
 Scleropages_for LQLQGRDRMITDMYDAVKAFAVQKLLWETQMRQCNLSHFPCQVM--LNQVGT----VF
 Syngnathus_acus LQLQGRDRMITDMYDAVKAFAVQKLLWETQMLQCNLSHFPCQVM--LNQVGT----VF
 Thalassophryne_ LQLQGRDRMITDMYDAVKAFAVQKLLWESQMHQCNMSHSPCCQVM--LNQAGT----VF
 Scophthalmus_ma LHLQGRDRITDMYDTVKAFAVQKLLWETQMRQSNLPHFPCCQVM--FNQVGAT----VF
 Xenopus_tropica -----
 Collichthys_luc KKLQGGQQLVSAAYDNVRAFSTKLVLWKAQLSQTNLCHFPACKAL--AD--AGT----PF
 Paralichthys_ol -----
 Cottoperca_gobi VKLQGGKQFVHDMYTNVRAFKSKLILFSRQMANKSFAHFPTLAMQ--KEAT-----R
 Alligator_missi SRLQEKGFLFAHELHSNIKSFMMLKLLFSRQIGNKDFSHFPTLQV--TVSD-----Q
 Parambassis_ran TKLQGGKGLFVHQMHSLVKAFAVQKLLSRQLESNTLTHMQTLKEV--TPSA-----D
 Perca_flavescen -----
 Gadus_morhua LQLQGRDQIITQLYDHFVRAFQKQLQLLNRHLLTGNLAHFPPLREV--GLME-----E
 Archocentrus VKMQGIGNTVLSLQAVFAFENKLELFIADIETGRLLHFKEKLF--KDACTASDPAQHL
 Takifugu KNLQGGQSTALHMLEEILAFERKMTVFARDVQNGTLSHFPSLREF--KEANNH-----I
 Oryzias_latipes TSLQGGKGTALHMLEEVLGFERKLVFATDLKRGTYHFPALREF--QQAGNA-----I
 Erpetoichthys LKLQGGKGNPAYVLEELVCFEKLILFAEDIQSGKLLHFQFLKQY--RDKTSAT-----V

Sphaeramia_orbi DSARYEEHVQSISSSEFERRFTDFASIEPIASYMCPYFGASIDVGDIAAKVKSFLDFESST
 Labrus_bergylta DSARYTEQIDKCLSEFDKHFQDFLLEPIATFMCPYFQEDAEVDSLASKISTLHFNSSG
 Labeo_rohita DNARYKEQIDNCLSEFDKRFQDFALLEPIATFMCPYFQEDAEVDSLASKIATLHFNSSG
 Xiphophorus NMGYVVKMLAQLYGSITSRFEDLQKRPQIALLIDPFNAEADCKSPLVT-----DEAA
 Xiphophorus_hel NMGYVVKMLAQLYGSITSRFEDLQKRPQIALLIDPFNAEADCKSPLVT-----DEAA
 Gouania_willden PAEKVEALEMLKAEFGVRFRELRVYAKEIRLFQNPVADIDEAQ-----PS
 Lates_calcarife PAEKVEALEMLKAEFGVRFRELRVYAKEIRLFQNPVADID-----
 Anolis_caroline PNKTCVDSLERLQKEFQFRFKEHLHEQDIQLFRNPFSIDIENV-----TI
 Kryptolebias_ma SCAQLATKLSWLKTEFDRRFSDFAQQSGFDIFANPFTTQVCTAP-----QH
 Anguilla_anguil SCARLATKLSRLMNEFDRRFSDFAQHSQGFIFASPFITDVSSAP-----HH
 Larimichthys_cr PFAQFAEKLLILGAEFTRRFADFEAQKRFELLSNPFAFDVNNAP-----SN
 Chelmon_rostrat PSAQFAEKINALSVEFSRRFADFEAQKRFELLSNLFAIDVESAP-----TS
 Maylandia_zebra PCAQFAEKLCVLSTEFTRWFADFEAQKRFELLSNPFAVDVAKAP-----TN
 Salvelinus_nama PCAQFAEKLSVLAAEFSRRFADFDVQKRFELLSNPFAVDVENAP-----TN
 Salmo_trutta PCAQFAEKLSVLAAEFSRRFADFDVQKRFELLSNPFAVDVENAP-----TN

Oncorhynchus_ki PCAQFAEKLSVLAAEFSSRRFADFDAQCKFELLSNPFVAVDVENAP-----TN
 Bufo_bufo PCAQFAEKLSVLGAEFSRRFADFVQKCRFELLSNPFVAVNVENAP-----TN
 malaclemys_terr PNATFAEKLSALRTEFARRFSDFEAQKSNFELLRNPFVAVDVEETAP-----VE
 Trachemys_scrip PNATFAEKLSALRTEFARRFSDFEAQKSNFELLRNPFVAVDVEETAP-----VE
 Etheostoma_spec PNATFAEKLSALRTEFARRFSDFEAQKSNFELLRNPFVAVDVEETAP-----VE
 Scleropages_for PNTHFADKLSAPRTEFARRFGDFEQQKNFELRNPFVAVDVEETAP-----VQ
 Syngnathus_acus PNTHFAVKLSALRTEFARRFGDFEQQKNFELRNPFVAVDVEETAP-----VQ
 Thalassophryne_ PNMHFADKLSALRTEFARRFGDFEQQKNLELLRNPFVAVDVEETAP-----VQ
 Scophthalmus_ma PNTHFADKLSALRTEFARRFGDF-----RNPFAVDVEETAP-----VQ
 Xenopus_tropica -----
 Collichthys_luc SGEKYVDVILKQLQEEFDHRFADFKTHRATFQIFADPPFSFDVQDAP-----PV
 Paralichthys_ol -----
 Cottoperca_gobi NVKKYCTSLDDMHREFCRRFSDFEKIDKSLQLVSCPLSQDPETAP-----HE
 Alligator_missi NLKKYVSLLDLHAEFSCRVEDFQMIKDLVSSPFTFNVD SAP-----CD
 Parambassis_ran HLRRYSSMLGALHGEFSRRFEDLRTIEDEMHISSPFTYSVDNAP-----TD
 Perca_flavescen -----
 Gadus_morhua DTPKYCNILSDLVVEFDHRFEDFHGNEAAFELFAQPFVAVNDAVS-----EE
 Archocentrus DLQQLAGFTSNLLQSFKARFGFRERSRLFKFITHPHECAVDSADLSYIPG---VSVRD
 Takifugu NCDYFHRAITAMQAAFEKRFSEFRKEKQTLSPVAPLNSDPSLLNTSAFTG---VSKPD
 Oryzias_latipes NSQYLKSVITAMQTSFGKRFCEFRQEKHTLSFPVPTLIDPSQLNMTAFAGV---VSQPD
 Erpetoichthys DTNYFSTVIKKIKDEFADRFEQFKTNKTLAFIVNPLNTNSNEIHLEPFG----IDTGS

Sphaeramia_orbi LEDEILTLQNDIEMKARSTSAQR-----GEH-----VFWKL
 Labrus_bergylda VEDEILTLQADIQLKSRA-----H-----GEFWNL
 Labeo_rohita VEDEILTLQADIQLKSRA-----H-----GQFWNL
 Xiphophorus SELEMVELREDDRLKSLKKEGPV-----AFWRV
 Xiphophorus_hel SELEMVELREDDRLKSLKKEGPV-----AFWRV
 Gouania_willden YQFELAEIQNCDVLDKDAFKPNSL-----INFYAA
 Lates_calcarife -----
 Anolis_caroline YQMELAEIQNCDLKDFAKPRSL-----PNFYAS
 Kryptolebias_ma LQMELIELQSDSGLKAKFQDAAI-----QDFYRL
 Anguilla_anguil LQLELIELQSDSGLRAKQDAAI-----EDFYRL
 Larimichthys_cr LQMELIELQCNDTLKSKYDSVGA-----AQFPPY
 Chelmon_rostrat LQMELIELQCNDMLKSKYDSVGA-----AQFPCF
 Maylandia_zebra LQMELIELQYSDTLKSKYNAVGA-----SQFPHF
 Salvelinus_nama IQMELIELQCNDTLKSKYDAVGA-----AQFPRF
 Salmo_trutta IQMELIELQCNDTLKSKYDAVGA-----AQFPRF
 Oncorhynchus_ki IQMELIELQCNDTLKSKYDAVGA-----AQFPRF
 Bufo_bufo LQMELIELQCNDTLKSKYDAVGA-----AQFPQF
 malaclemys_terr MQMELIELQCNGTLKAKYDTAGP-----AQFTRF
 Trachemys_scrip MQMELIELQCNGTLKAKYDTAGP-----AQFTRF
 Etheostoma_spec MQMELIELQCNGTLKAKYDTAGP-----AQFTRF
 Scleropages_for IQMELIELQCNGTLKAKYDTAGP-----AQFIHS
 Syngnathus_acus IQMELIELQCNGTLKSKYDTAGP-----TEFIHS
 Thalassophryne_ IQMKLIELQCNGTLKAKYDTAGP-----PQFIHA
 Scophthalmus_ma IQMELIELQCNGTLKAKYDTAGP-----AQFIRS
 Xenopus_tropica IQMELIELQCNGTLKAKYDTAGP-----AQFIHS
 Collichthys_luc LQMELIDLQCNSELKAKFREVSQKVDK-----LGQFLRE
 Paralichthys_ol -----
 Cottoperca_gobi LQLELIDLQSDSVSQEFKSLKL-----NDFYAS
 Alligator_missi LQLELIDLQYDALLAEQFQAVPL-----PSFYAS

Parambassis_ran VQLELIDLQSDAVLAEHFKSGSL-----LDFYST
 Perca_flavescen -----
 Gadus_morhua LQMELLELSQSDSLCCRFRELPL-----QDFYKS
 Archocentrus FELQVADLKASDMWVWVKFKSLNEDLERLAQQQAE LASKHKW GEMKKLQPADQLIVKTWKA
 Takifugu LEIE LADIADKVLWVWVKFKSL SADLEEVVRQRATLAKEHKWSDMEQLPQPKLIFATWNA
 Oryzias_latipes LEMELADI-----WVFKFKSLTAYLENVSRQKAVLAQNHKWSDIANLPKQDKLVFETWNA
 Erpetoichthys LEMQLIDLKSKALWSGKFTLKSLEELVQKYMVYVTTQKWTALKEMPRVEALIFDAWNS

Sphaeramia_orbi LVAEKYPNLRRCALNLTALFGSTYLCESAF SHMNIISKYRSTMTDDHLAACLRLATSS-
 Labrus_bergylda LTEEKYPNMRKCATSLTALFGSTYLCESAF SHMKIISKYRSTITDGHLEVCLRLAVSS-
 Labeo_rohita LTEEKYPNMRKCATSLTALFGSTYLCESAF SHMKIISKYRSTMTDDHLEVCLRLAISS-
 Xiphophorus VPTEKYPCVKRAALKLLSMFSSSTYVCELSFSTLKHVKSKHRSVLTDTHVKELLRVATTE-
 Xiphophorus_he1 VPTEKYPCVKRAALKLLSMFSSSTYVCELSFSTLKHVKSKHRSVLTDTHVKELLRVATTE-
 Gouania_willden LPNDTYPNIKKHAMKMSTLFGSTYICEQTF SHMKHLKTPTRSRLTDEHLHQCLRLAVTR-
 Lates_calcarife -----
 Anolis_caroline LPSETYPNLRNHALKMATIFGSTYVCEQTF SRMKHLKSPTRSRLTDAHLHLLRLAVTN-
 Kryptolebias_ma MPPGLMPQLRLHAARVLSMFGSTYLCEQFFSMMNLNKNQHRSLTDDNLHAVLRIASAQD
 Anguilla_anguil LPPGVMPQLRLHAARVLSMFGSTYLCEQMF SIMNLNKT KHRSLTDDNLHAVLRIATAQE
 Larimichthys_cr L-PDTLPELRAQAAQMLSMFGSTYLCEQLFSLMKMNKTPHRSRLTDEHLHSVLRISSAQS
 Chelmon_rostrat L-PDTMPQLRTQAAQMLSMFGSTYLCEQLFSSMMKVNKTPHRSRLTDEHLHSVLRISSAQS
 Maylandia_zebra I-PDTMPQLRTHAAQMLSMFGSTYLCEQLFSSMKMAKTSHRRRLTDEHLHSILRISSAQS
 Salvelinus_nama I-SDTMPQLRTQAAQMLSMFGSTYLCEQLFSSMKMTKTTHRRRLTDEHLRSILRISSAQR
 Salmo_trutta I-PDTMPQLRTQAAQMLSMFGSTYLCEQLFSSMKMTKTTHRRRLTDEHLRSILRISSAQS
 Oncorhynchus_ki I-PDTMPQLRTQAAQMLSMFGSTYLCEQLFSSMKMTKTTHRRRLTDEHLRSILRISSAQS
 Bufo_bufo I-PDTMPQLRTQAAQMLSMFGSTYLCEQLFSSMKMTKTTHRRRLTDEHLRSILRISSAQS
 malaclemys_terr I-PEAMQQLRQHAARILSMFGSTYLCEQLF SVMKINKTSHRSRLTDEHLQSILRIFTTQN
 Trachemys_scrip I-PEAMPQLRQHAARILSMFGSTYLCEQLF SVMKINKTSHRSRLTDEHLQSILRIFTTQN
 Etheostoma_spec L-PEAMPQLRQHAARILSMFGSTYSGAQKFTYTCLS-----
 Scleropages_for I-PAEMPQLRLHAARTLCMFGSTYLCEKLF SVMKTNKTAHGSRLTDEHLQSILRISTTQN
 Syngnathus_acus I-PAAMSQRLRLHVARTLCMFGSTYLCEKLF SVMKTNKTAHRSRLTDEHLQSILRVSTTRD
 Thalassophryne_ I-PAEMPQLRLHVARTLCMFGSTYLCEKLF SVMKTNKTAHRSRLTDEHLQSILRISTTQK
 Scophthalmus_ma I-PETMPQLRLHAAQTLCMFGSTYLCEKLF SVMKMNKTAHRSRLTDGHLQSILRISTAQE
 Xenopus_tropica I-PAEMPQLRLHAARTLCMFGSTYLCEKLL SVMKTNKTAHRRHLTDEHLQSILRIST-QN
 Collichthys_luc L-TPSFPELSRMFKRTMCLFGSTYLCEKLFSTLNFNKS KYRSRLTDDHLQAILRVSTASS
 Paralichthys_ol -----
 Cottoperca_gobi LNEATFPNLRRTAQKMLALFGSTYVCEQAF SVMNINKARHRSRLTDQHLSILRIATTK-
 Alligator_missi LNEQKFPKIKTHARKMLVLFGSTYVCEQTR SVMKVNKSNLRSMSGDHLAAVLR IATTE-
 Parambassis_ran LKEENFPNMRRHAQKMLVLFGSTYICEQTF SMMKFAKSTHRSRLTDDHLSAVLRISTSN-
 Perca_flavescen -----
 Gadus_morhua VPAHRYGKIRKHAQVMFSLFGSTYVCEQAFSLMNLNKS KLRNALSDSHLHDILTLVSQ-
 Archocentrus L-PVTYHTLQRVSI AVLTMFGSTYACEQSF SHLKNIKTNLRSRLTDGSLNSCMKLNLT-
 Takifugu I-PDITYNMKRCAFGVLSIFGSTYLCEQVFSMNIISKYRSRFTSETLQSCVMKMKVTS-
 Oryzias_latipes I-PDSYINMKRYAFGVLEIFGSTYICEQVFSNVNFIKNKHSRSLTHISLR SCLKMKVTS-
 Erpetoichthys L-PDCYSEVKKLAFGVLTIFGSTYS-----

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Sphaeramia_orbi YTPNYEK LASSS-QCQVSH-----
 Labrus_bergylda YCPDYASLADSI-QCKSSE-----
 Labeo_rohita YCPDYASLADSI-QCKSSE-----
 Xiphophorus YQPD LQRITRNK-RCQKSH-----
 Xiphophorus_he1 YQPD LQRITRNK-RCQKSH-----

Gouania_willden MEPDINLLTSQM-QAHSSH-----
Lates_calcarife -----
Anolis_caroline MEPDIDYLSQK-QAHSSH-----
Kryptolebias_ma LKPDIDTLATGK-RCQTSQGKNTG---
Anguilla_anguil LKPDIDTLAKGK-RCQTSGQKTH----
Larimichthys_cr LTPDIDALACKK-RCQVSGLDPCASSE
Chelmon_rostrat LTPDLDELASKK-RCQVSGLDQCAE--
Maylandia_zebra LSPDIEELASKK-RCQVSGLDASE---
Salvelinus_nama LSPDIDELPSKK-RCQVSGLGTSD---
Salmo_trutta LSPDIDELASKK-RCQVSGLGTSD---
Oncorhynchus_ki LSPDIDELASKK-RCQVSGLGTSD---
Bufo_bufo LSPDIDELSSKK-RCQVSGLGTSD---
malaclemys_terr LTPNINELVAKK-RLQVSGSD-----
Trachemys_scrip LTPNINELVAKK-RLQVSGSD-----
Etheostoma_spec -----
Scleropages_for LTPNINELVAKK-RCQASSSDKMT---
Syngnathus_acus LTPNINQLVAKK-RCQSSGSDKMA---
Thalassophryne_ LTPNIKELVAKK-RCQASSFDKTT---
Scophthalmus_ma LTPNLNDLTAKK-RCQTSKSDKMA---
Xenopus_tropica LTPNINLNFV---CQASSSDKMT---
Collichthys_luc LHPNVARLCERR-RCQVSGSKK-----
Paralichthys_ol -----
Cottoperca_gobi LTPDFDALAKKGDQQHCSH-----
Alligator_missi MTPDFDFLVNAHQRLHSSP-----
Parambassis_ran IQPDFDALVKAQQRLDFTH-----
Perca_flavescen -----REQSVYGGHGH---
Gadus_morhua LEPDINRLVKTCDRLHVSH-----
Archocentrus YQPDYKAISKTM-QHQKSH-----
Takifugu YSADIGKICREM-QTKSH-----
Oryzias_latipes YSPDVKKLCSEV-QEQKSH-----
Erpetoichthys -----